

Hades2D Soccer2D Simulation Team Description Paper 2024 for IranOpen2024

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Abstract. The Soccer2D Simulated League is one of the leagues of the RoboCup competitions. In Soccer2D Simulation, each simulated robot player may have its own play strategy and every simulated team consists of a collection of programs. This article contains descriptions of Hades2D activities in 2023-2024. This year our team tried to improve the starter base [1][2] defense and offense strategies such as shoot, mark, formation, goalie.

Keywords: Soccer simulation 2D, Robocup 2024, defense strategy.

1 Introduction

RoboCup is an international scientific initiative that aims to improve the capabilities of intelligent robots. The goals of the 2D soccer simulation league are as follows: First is the development of simulators that form the infrastructure of the simulation system and simulate realistic phenomena prevailing in disasters; The second is the development of intelligent agents and robots that can play a role in disaster response scenarios.

Last year, we participated in IranOpen and RoboCup as Hermes2D [3]. This time, we are going to participate as Hades2D. So far, we have worked on defensive strategies such as formation, goalie, mark and we also worked on shoot. In the future, we plan to improve dribble, block, pass and other strategies in the base code.

1.1 Activities Done by Other Iranian Teams

In this section, we will mention some ideas presented in previous year's SS2D Iranian teams' TDPs.

Cyrus2023 presented a denoising idea powered by long short-term memory networks (LSTM) and deep neural networks (DNN).[4]

Damavand2023 used a deep neural network (DNN) model for dribble.[5]

Emperor2023 used Perceptron Algorithm for through pass strategy.[6]

Hades2D2023 considered some conditions to improve shoot and pass strategy.[7]

Robo2023 used Voronoi Diagram algorithm for trough pass. [8]

R3CESBU2023 divided the field into 5 parts and made a strategy for the goalie's position. They also implemented a function for calculating opponent danger score. [9]

The82023 discussed decision-making system that uses a fuzzy algorithm based on ball position and player situation to determine the appropriate pass type (Secure, Normal, Risky). [10]

2 Team

2.1 Formation

Formation is the placement of players in the positions. We use last year's major defense formation in our half of the field and last year's major offense formation in the opponent's half of the field. We used Fedit tool to arrange players [11].

In this formation, we define 31 circles in the playground (we chose circle because it leads to fewer number of areas compared to triangle or rectangle area so the implementation would be easier) and place the players in each circle based on the ball position. If the ball is in the circles, the players will move to their defined places. However, due to the rectangular nature of the field, it is not possible for the field to be covered by circles; so, if the ball is in a position not covered by the circles, the players will consider the ball's previous circle. As the ball approaches the goals, player density increases, whereas it decreases as the ball approach the halfway line. We are still working on the code and had not debug it yet.

Fig 1. The mentioned circles.

2.2 Goalie

At first, our initial idea was written based on the experience we had in previous games on the assumption that if the opponent with the ball gets close to the goal, the goalkeeper will go towards him, but the opponent may suddenly pass to his teammate to shoot, and in this case, the goalkeeper will not have time to reach the ball. So, our idea Based on this incident, it was written in such a way that the goalie should stand between two players close to the goal to make it possible to reach both.

This idea was sometimes not implemented properly because the player with the ball was not necessarily the closest player, so we created another mode where the goalie stands between the player with the ball and the closest player.

2.3 Mark

Marking is the act of closely guarding an opponent player to prevent them from receiving the ball or making a play. Our strategy is straightforward: each player ascertains whether they are the closest to one of the opponents. If so, then they are going to hard-mark that specific opponent.

However, this simple act has its own challenges. How can I make sure that I am the closest teammate? What course of action should be taken if, after 10 marking cycles, I am no longer the closest player? Should I keep marking the same opponent or the new one? Furthermore, how will my teammate notice my new decision? Is it better to hard-mark, soft-mark or make a defensive wall? Does my action help or am I just wasting stamina? We aim to solve problems like these in the future.

2.4 Shoot

Our shooting strategy is that players should quickly assess the situation by considering factors such as their position on the field, the distance to the goal, the position of shooter and the goalkeeper, the angle of the player's body in relation to the goal, and find the best spot to shoot. In addition, our strategy is by dividing the goal into 13 separate points, assigning scores to each point based on the aforementioned factors and finally shoots by choosing the point with the highest score. The accuracy of our scoring system means that no point has the same score. Lastly, since timing and accuracy are key elements, dividing the goal into more points increases the game processing and reduces the performance speed, so dividing the goal into 13 points was the best choice.

Before the player shoots, he checks whether another player has a better chance of scoring a goal. If he can pass to him, he does so; otherwise, he will shoot himself. We call this action a "pass shoot" that we are still working on.

Fig 2. The shooter is finding the best point.

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